

Mechanisms of Cooperative Dynamics Emerging in Interrole Conflict Situations

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Abstract: This study explores how people manage conflict when they belong to multiple groups and decide which groups to support at a given time. We introduced a computer simulation called the interrole conflict game to mimic real-life situations in which individuals face competing demands. To represent the differences between adolescence and adulthood, we used Recurrent Q-Learning (RQL) agents that adjusted behavior based on past experiences. Our findings show that an agent's ability to cooperate depends on how well it can predict future actions. When agents have a limited memory, they perform better by focusing on immediate rewards. In contrast, when agents can remember more information, they can plan ahead and work together more effectively over time. We also observed that gradual adjustments in the learning process using a low learning rate helped the agents become more stable and cooperative. This study provides insight into how short-term reactions and long-term planning can be balanced to improve cooperation in complex social settings.

Keywords: Adolescent Characteristics, Cooperative Dynamics, Interrole-Conflict Game, Recurrent Q-Learning, Multi-Agent Simulation.

I. INTRODUCTION

People can typically be classified as belonging to multiple groups, and in such situations, interrole conflicts" may occur. As shown in Fig. 1, interrole conflict occurs when people belonging to multiple groups are simultaneously requested to work by these groups [1-2]. In addition, interrole conflicts frequently occur in places where people belonging to multiple groups gather, regardless of their roles and age categories such as adolescence, adulthood, and so on. In other words, interrole conflicts occur not only after the developmental stage of adulthood but also in adolescent groups. However, most studies on interrole conflict have focused on adult subjects.

Fig. 1 Interrole conflict situation in which a person requests work simultaneously and belongs to many groups.

Adolescence, the period between childhood and adulthood, is a time when ego identity is formed and the mental and physical foundations of life after adolescence are built [3]. In contrast, in early adulthood, the prefrontal cortex matures, suppressing impulsive behavior and playing an important role in executing plans in proper order [4]. The inability of adolescents to perform actions in an orderly and systematic manner is thought to be due to the immaturity of their prefrontal cortex. It has also been found that differences in the degree of development of these brain regions cause peculiar behavioral characteristics from an adolescent perspective [5]. As mentioned above, adolescents exhibit characteristics that differ from those of adults. Therefore, focusing only on adulthood to elucidate the emergence and transformation processes of coping strategies is insufficient for alleviating interrole conflicts that cause various problems. In other words, we must prepare multiple populations organized by dividing human subjects according to their adolescent and adult characteristics and observe the interactions among the groups for a prolonged period.

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When such experiments with human subjects are difficult, a Multi-Agent Simulation (MAS) experiment can demonstrate its true potential. However, there are almost no studies concerning interrole conflicts targeting both adolescence and adulthood using the MAS, except for our previous studies [6-7]. Building on studies in which we introduced the Interrole Conflict Game (ICG), a novel game-theoretic framework, and employed agents representing adolescent and adult traits, we analyzed how the agents' parameters affect cooperation emergence in the ICG. Our findings in our previous studies [6-7] indicated that both typical adolescent traits (high learning and low discount rates) and time-series learning and prediction abilities (linked to prefrontal cortex functions) are crucial for coping with interrole conflicts and fostering equal cooperation.

However, these studies could not clarify the mechanisms of ICG dynamics during peak cooperation. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to clarify these mechanisms based on an analysis of their dynamics. Elucidating the mechanisms of cooperation in the ICG may lead to solutions for interrole conflicts that arise even after adulthood. This is also extremely important in pursuing good physical, mental, and social conditions, namely well-being.

II. INTERROLE CONFLICT GAME

A. An interrole conflict expressed by game-theoretic framework

As shown in Fig. 1, interrole conflict occurs when people belonging to multiple groups are requested to perform work simultaneously. To express this interrole conflict situation as a game-theoretic framework, the following three conditions must be met: 1) people belong to multiple groups; 2) they can cooperate with only one group at a time; and 3) they can benefit from the cooperation of others, except for themselves. That is, condition 3) implies that individuals cannot gain rewards through their own actions alone, but only when others choose to cooperate with the individual's group. This interdependence creates a dilemma, as players must rely on others' decisions, which may conflict with their own group commitments. However, no game met all three conditions. Therefore, in our previous study [6], we proposed an interrole conflict game (ICG) with the above three characteristics as a novel game that expresses interrole conflict situations.

Fig. 2 Schematic of an interrole conflict game (ICG) minimum configuration, in which there are three players and three groups, and the maximum number of groups to which each person belongs is two.

Fig. 2 shows a schematic diagram of the minimum configuration of the ICG when the number of players and groups are three each, and the maximum number of groups to which each person belongs is two. In this study, we used an ICG with the minimum configuration, as illustrated in Fig. 2.

Players of the ICG can receive three types of rewards: 1) R^+ when $S > 1$, 2) 0 when $S = 1$, and 3) R^- when $S < 1$, where S is the bare minimum number of cooperative people in a group, R^+ is a positive reward, and R^- is a negative reward. The sum of the rewards received from all the groups to which the player belongs is given to that player. For example, as shown in Fig. 2, the player-A who belongs to both group 1 and 2 receives " $R^+ + R^-$," whereas player-B who belongs to both group 2 and 3 receives " $0 + R^-$," and player-C who belongs to both group 1 and 3 receives " $R^+ + 0$."

Based on the reward function, the optimal solution in the ICG with the minimum configuration rotates the three groups in turn such that the two players cooperate in each group.

B. Recurrent Q-learning agents with characteristics of adolescence and adulthood as players of the ICG

We adopted Recurrent Q-Learning (RQL) agents [8] as the ICG players. RQL [8] is a hybrid learning method that combines Q-learning [9-10], which is a reinforcement learning method, with a recurrent neural network (RNN) as a learning framework with time-series learning and prediction capabilities [11]. We used a modified model [12] of the Elman-net [13] as the RNN architecture. The ϵ -greedy policy [9-10] was adopted as the method for selecting actions. A schematic diagram of the learning process flow in RQL is shown in Fig.3.

As can be seen in Fig.3, first, the RNNs of RQL agents receive the actions of the opponents at time $t-1$, output their Q-values, which represent the worth of the agents' actions, and select one of the actions based on the Q-values by using the ϵ -greedy policy. Thereafter, rewards are received, and their Q-values are renewed using Q-learning. Finally, in the RQL, the renewed Q-values become the teacher signals for the RNN, and the RNN learns to output the renewed Q-values using the back-propagation method with a learning rate η .

Fig. 3 Schematic diagram of the learning process flow in recurrent Q-learning. The numbers circled from 1 to 7 represent the processing order.

In ICG, each player selects one group to which they belong, and cooperates by themselves during every step. Therefore, the types of player actions are identical to the number of groups to which they belong. The states that are necessary to select an action are the group numbers selected by all players at time $t-1$.

Differences in characteristics of adolescence and adulthood can be represented by settings of three parameters in the RQL agents: the learning rate η of the RNN and the learning and discount rates of the Q-learning, namely, α and γ , respectively. Two types of learning rates can be interpreted as follows; α is the amount of change that determines how fast the target Q-value can be approached, and η is the amount of change that determines how large to change the weight of each connection line of the RNN that outputs the updated Q-value.

III. RESULTS

A. Settings of the simulation experiments

The common parameters used in all the ICG simulation experiments are listed in Table 1, and Table 2 depicts the settings when peak cooperation emerged in three types of number of hidden neurons.

Table 1 Common settings of simulation experiments.

The maximum number of steps	1,000,000
The number of players (agents)	3
The number of groups	3
The number of groups to which one player can belong	2
The bare minimum number of cooperation in a group S	1
Rewards R^+ and R^-	+1 and -1
The degree of randomness ϵ in action selection for the ϵ -greedy policy	0.1
The number of output neurons in RNN	2
The number of input neurons in RNN	3
The maximum number of learning for one data set in the BP for RNN	10,000

Table 2 Settings of simulation experiments when peak cooperation emerged.

The number of hidden (context) neurons in RNN	1	5	10
Learning rate α for Q-learning	0.6	0.8	0.9
Discount rate γ for Q-learning	0.1	0.8	0.7
Learning rate η used by the BP for RNN	0.1	0.1	0.1

B. Results of the simulation experiments

B-1. Comparisons of the dynamics in the ICG

In our previous study [8], we found that the maximum number of cooperation in cases where the settings of the number of hidden neurons in the RQL agents were 1, 5 and 10, were 302720, 306646, and 311466, respectively. The other settings for these cases are listed in Table 2.

First, we focused on clarifying the dynamics of the ICG when peak cooperation emerged. To realize this, we confirmed the dynamics of transitions of the eight types of interrole conflict patterns when peak cooperation emerged for every three types of hidden neurons, as illustrated in Table 2. The simplified schematics of the patterns and rewards obtained by each agent in each pattern are listed in Table 3.

Fig. 4 Transitional examples of the eight types of interrole conflict patterns in case that the maximum number of cooperation is earned in the RQL agents' settings that the number of hidden neurons is 1, the learning rate α for Q-learning is 0.6, the discount rate γ for Q-learning is 0.1, ϵ of the ϵ -greedy policy is 0.1, and the learning rate η for RNN is 0.1, respectively. The x-axis is step, and the y-axis is the number of interrole conflict patterns.

Table 3 Correspondence among eight patterns of interrole conflicts, its schematics, and rewards that each agent obtains in each pattern.

Eight patterns of interrole-conflicts	Schematics of ICG	Rewards		
		agent-0 (A)	agent-1 (B)	agent-2 (C)
0		0	0	0
1		1	-1	0
2		-1	0	1
3		0	-1	1
4		0	1	-1
5		1	0	-1
6		-1	1	0
7		0	0	0

Figs. 4-6 show transitional examples of the patterns when the maximum number of cooperation is earned in the RQL agent settings, where the number of hidden neurons is 1, 5 and 10, respectively. The three sampling intervals shown in each Fig. are 0 to 1000, 500000 to 501000 and 999000 to 1000000 steps.

The settings, except for the number of hidden neurons in RNN, in Fig. 4 are as follows: the learning rate α for Q-learning is 0.6, the discount rate γ for Q-learning is 0.1, ϵ of the ϵ -greedy policy is 0.1, and the learning rate η for RNN is 0.1.

Fig. 4 shows that each pattern, except for Patterns 0 and 7, was repeated individually many times in succession. The transition from one pattern to another was irregular and non-periodic. The non-periodic transitions have three types of causes: 1) random actions based on the ϵ -greedy policy, 2) action values of changes by Q-learning and 3) irregular changes of actions by the chaos system [12] in which the RNNs can obtain through the BP-learning.

In addition, although somewhat fewer in number, the two-period dynamics of patterns 1 and 3, 2 and 6, and 4 and 5 occur in succession in several steps.

The settings, except for the number of hidden neurons in RNN, in Fig. 5 are as follows: the learning rate α for Q-learning is 0.8, the discount rate γ for Q-learning is 0.8, ϵ of the ϵ -greedy policy is 0.1, and the learning rate η for RNN is 0.1.

Fig. 5 Transitional examples of the eight types of interrole conflict patterns in a case where the maximum number of cooperation is earned in the RQL agents' settings such that the number of hidden neurons is 5, the learning rate α for Q-learning is 0.8, the discount rate γ for Q-learning is 0.8, ϵ of the ϵ -greedy policy is 0.1, and the learning rate η for RNN is 0.1. The x - and y -axes are the same as that of Fig. 4.

Fig. 6 Transitional examples of the eight types of interrole conflict patterns in a case where the maximum number of cooperation is earned in the RQL agents' settings such that the number of hidden neurons is 10, the learning rate α for Q-learning is 0.9, the discount rate γ for Q-learning is 0.7, ϵ of the ϵ -greedy policy is 0.1, and the learning rate η for RNN is 0.1. The x - and y -axes are the same as that of Fig. 4.

By comparing Figs. 4 and 5, we observed that each pattern except for patterns 0 and 7 was repeated individually many times in succession in Fig. 5, like in Fig. 4. Moreover, we found that various combinations of two-periodic dynamics emerge with patterns 1 and 3, 2 and 6, and 4 and 5, which continue longer than those in Fig. 4.

Fig. 6 shows the transitional dynamics when peak cooperation emerges for RQL agents with 10 hidden neurons. The settings of the agents are as follows: the learning rate α for Q-learning is 0.9, the discount rate γ for Q-learning is 0.7, ϵ of the ϵ -greedy policy is 0.1, and the learning rate η for RNN is 0.1.

The various types of two-period dynamics shown in Figs. 4 and 5 are illustrated in Fig. 6. The duration of the dynamics in Fig. 6 is significantly different from those in Figs. 4 and 5. As can be seen in Fig. 6, we observed that the two-periodic dynamics with patterns 1 and 3, 2 and 6, and 4 and 5 continue even longer than those in Fig. 5.

B-2. Comparisons of occurrence frequencies of each patterns and the transitional dynamics in the ICG

Next, we analyzed the transitional dynamics and extracted the dominant periodic patterns. In Figs. 4-6, we found that each pattern, except for patterns 0 and 7, was not only repeated individually many times in succession, but also two-periodic dynamics with patterns 1 and 3, 2 and 6, and 4 and 5 emerged. As shown in Table 3, agents 0, 1, and 2 switched patterns between 2 and 6, patterns between 1 and 3, and patterns between 4 and 5, respectively. Therefore, we confirmed the occurrence frequency of the three-period dynamics and have shown the results of 12 types of dominant patterns extracted from all patterns in Figs. 7-9.

Fig. 7 illustrates the results for the RQL agents with one hidden neuron. Continuous individual fixed-point patterns from 2 to 6 were even more dominant in the overall transition dynamics. As shown in Table 3, when continuous individual fixed-point patterns emerge, except for patterns 0 and 7, only one agent can continue obtaining positive rewards, and negative rewards are continuously given to another agent.

Fig. 7 Occurrence frequency of dominant patterns of three-period dynamics where peak cooperation emerges in the RQL agents’ settings such that the number of hidden neurons is 1.

Fig. 8 shows the results for the RQL agents with five hidden neurons. By comparing Figs. 7 and 8, we observed the reverses between the occurrence frequencies of continuous individual fixed-point patterns and three-period patterns. In the case of three-period patterns, negative rewards were given to only

one agent, and the remaining two agents received positive rewards alternately. Therefore, an agent who receives negative rewards is a key player in switching a point-getter to another agent.

Fig. 8 Occurrence frequency of dominant patterns of three-period dynamics where peak cooperation emerges in the RQL agents’ settings such that the number of hidden neurons is 5.

Fig. 9 shows the results for RQL agents with 10 hidden neurons. It was observed that the occurrence frequency of three-period patterns in Fig. 9 was not much different from that in Fig. 8. However, the frequency of continuous individual fixed-point patterns significantly reduced, although there was considerable variation. This pattern stabilized the scoring rotation between the two individuals. However, this is not an optimal rotating pattern, allowing each of the three individuals to score one point.

Fig. 9 Occurrence frequency of dominant patterns of three-period dynamics where peak cooperation emerges in the RQL agents’ settings such that the number of hidden neurons is 10.

IV. DISCUSSION

In this section, we discuss the dynamics of the ICG, its strategy, the relationship between them, and the parameters of the RQL agents.

The ICG is designed to model situations in which an individual belongs to multiple groups, but is only allowed

to cooperate with one group at a time. The optimal state is reached when each group receives a balanced rotation of cooperation, meaning that every player takes turns to obtain a reward. Because each player's decision affects and is affected by the decisions of others, a trade-off exists regarding how each player allocates their cooperative efforts. The design of the reward function also makes the system susceptible to fixed-point patterns if continuous successes or failures occur, potentially locking the system into nonoptimal states.

The RQL agent integrates a traditional Q-learning algorithm with a recurrent neural network (RNN) to capture temporal patterns in opponents' actions. This hybrid approach allows the agent to not only react to immediate rewards, but also learn and predict long-term sequences of behavior. The learning rate α (in Q-learning) determines how quickly an agent updates its Q-values. A higher α value makes the agent more reactive to recent rewards, representing the impulsiveness and risk-taking associated with adolescence. The discount rate γ represents the degree to which future rewards are valued. A lower γ value makes the agent more short-sighted, again reflecting adolescent tendencies, whereas a higher γ value corresponds to more future-oriented, adult-like behavior. The learning rate η , used in the RNN's backpropagation, affects how rapidly the network adapts its weights based on sequential data. This parameter is crucial for an agent's ability to predict a future state.

The simulations revealed that the agents exhibited eight distinct interrole conflict patterns. Among these, fixed-point patterns (in which a player continuously receives either positive or negative rewards) and periodic dynamics (both two- and three-period cycles) are notable. The frequency and duration of these patterns depend on the internal parameters of the RQL agent. When the RNN had only one hidden neuron, a very low discount rate ($\gamma = 0.1$) maximized the number of cooperative actions. This suggests that with limited memory capacity and predictive ability, relying on immediate rewards is more effective. Conversely, when the number of hidden neurons was increased to 5 or 10, the agents captured more complex temporal patterns. In these cases, higher discount rates ($\gamma = 0.8$ and 0.7 , respectively) produced the highest cooperation, as the agents were better able to use long-term predictions to inform their actions.

With only one hidden neuron, an RNN has limited capacity to capture long-term dependencies. Thus, the agent performs better by focusing on short-term rewards, which is why a low discount rate ($\gamma = 0.1$) is most effective for maximizing cooperation. However,

when the capacity of the RNN increases (with 5 or 10 hidden neurons), it can extract and use more complex time-series patterns. This enhanced predictive ability makes it beneficial for the agent to value future rewards more, leading to higher cooperation when γ is set at 0.8 (for 5 neurons) or 0.7 (for 10 neurons).

When the RNN's learning rate η is set too high (e.g., 0.9), the weight updates during backpropagation become too large, making the learning process unstable and overly sensitive to recent errors [7]. This instability prevents RNN from accurately capturing long-term patterns, thereby reducing the effectiveness of cooperative strategies [7]. A lower learning rate (e.g., 0.1) results in smoother and more gradual updates. This stability helps the RNN consolidate information over time and accurately learn the temporal patterns required to forecast future states, ultimately leading to a greater number of cooperative actions. A lower η value also reduces the influence of random fluctuations or noise in the learning process, allowing the agents to maintain a more consistent and robust cooperative strategy.

V. CONCLUSION

Few studies have examined interrole conflict among adolescents. Thus, this study investigated differences in coping abilities between adolescents and adults in interrole conflict situations. Building on our previous study [6-7] where we introduced the ICG, a novel game-theoretic framework, and employed RQL agents representing adolescent and adult traits, we analyzed how the agents' parameters affect cooperation emergence in the ICG. Our findings indicate that not only a high learning rate and low discount rate that cause typical adolescent characteristics, including risk-taking, impulsivity, and novelty seeking [14-18], but also time-series learning and predicting abilities (linked to prefrontal cortex functions) are crucial for coping with interrole conflict and fostering equal cooperation [6-7].

In this study, we focused on clarifying the dynamics of the ICG when peak cooperation emerged. From simulation results, we found that when the RNN has limited capacity (only 1 hidden neuron), the agent is more effective when relying on short-term rewards (low discount rate, $\gamma = 0.1$), as it cannot capture long-term dependencies well. In contrast, with a greater RNN capacity (5 or 10 hidden neurons), agents can leverage more sophisticated time-series predictions, making higher discount rates ($\gamma = 0.8$ or 0.7) more effective in maximizing cooperation. Lower values of the RNN learning rate ($\eta = 0.1$) lead to more stable and gradual weight updates during backpropagation. This stability improves the network's ability to learn and

predict long-term patterns, which in turn fosters a higher number of cooperative actions compared to higher η values (0.9 or 0.5).

The simulation demonstrated that cooperative behavior in ICG is strongly influenced by the agents' internal parameters. The interplay between short-term reactivity and long-term predictive capability, mirroring adolescent versus adult characteristics, is critical for optimizing cooperation. Future research should integrate these simulation results with empirical data and neurobiological findings to develop more refined models of cooperation and tailored interventions based on individual characteristics.

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